

Factors Influencing Consumer Adoption of Electric Vehicles in India

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Abstract

The challenge of global warming necessitates the adoption of eco-friendly solutions to reduce dependence on fossil fuels. In India, the rising costs and environmental impact of fossil fuels have driven the search for alternative energy sources, especially in the transportation sector. Electric Vehicles (EVs) offer a viable solution, yet electric two-wheelers (E2Ws) constitute a small proportion of vehicle sales in India. This study aims to identify the primary factors influencing customer adoption of E2Ws in India. Data was collected via a structured questionnaire administered to 220 respondents and analysed using statistical methods. The findings highlight the importance of price, charging infrastructure, environmental awareness, social reinforcement, and perceived economic benefits in driving E2W adoption.

Keywords Electric Vehicle Adoption, Sustainability, Consumer Perception, Eco-friendly Transportation, Carbon Emissions.

Introduction

The electric vehicle (EV) market has experienced substantial global growth, although its penetration in India remains limited. In 2020, global EV sales reached 10 million, accounting for just 1% of total vehicle sales, while electric two-wheelers (E2Ws) saw higher adoption in Asia due to economic growth in countries like India, China, and Japan. India's automotive sector is dominated by two-wheelers, comprising over 80% of vehicle sales. The Indian government aims for 30% of all vehicles sold by 2030 to be electric, but adoption of E2Ws is currently under 1%.

The environmental impact of traditional vehicles in India is significant, with transportation being a major contributor to carbon emissions. EVs, producing 50% fewer greenhouse gases than conventional vehicles, offer a sustainable alternative. This study explores factors influencing the adoption of E2Ws, focusing on price, charging infrastructure, environmental awareness, social reinforcement and perceived economic benefits.

Objective of study The objective of this paper is to study and analyse the factors which is influencing consumer adoption of Electric Vehicles in India.

Review of Literature

Price

The high initial cost of EVs, primarily due to battery expenses and lack of economies of scale, is a significant barrier. Consumers with limited financial resources may opt for cheaper alternatives, hindering E2W adoption. Manufacturers need to achieve economies of scale to lower production costs and prices.

Charging Infrastructure

The availability of charging stations is crucial for EV adoption. Inadequate infrastructure can deter potential buyers. Urban areas, particularly large cities, require substantial investment in public charging facilities to support the growing EV market.

Environmental Awareness

Environmental concern drives consumer interest in EVs. Consumers aware of the environmental benefits of EVs are more likely to adopt them. EVs help reduce greenhouse gas emissions and dependence on fossil fuels, aligning with global sustainability goals.

Social Reinforcement

Social influences, including opinions from friends and family, significantly affect purchasing decisions. Positive reinforcement and social acceptance of EVs can enhance their adoption. Consumers seek validation from their social circle before making significant purchases.

Perceived Economic Benefits

The long-term economic benefits of EVs, such as lower maintenance and fuel costs, attract consumers. Despite the high initial cost, the potential savings on operating expenses make EVs a cost-effective choice over time.

Methodology

This study employs a quantitative research design to identify factors influencing E2W adoption in India. Data were collected using an online questionnaire targeting 220 urban respondents.

Sampling

The sample comprised 220 respondents, selected through convenient sampling from urban populations across India.

Data Collection Method

Primary data were obtained via a structured questionnaire, encompassing demographic information and factors related to E2W adoption.

Tools Used

Data analysis was conducted using statistical software. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic characteristics, while inferential statistics identified key factors influencing E2W adoption.

Analysis

Demographic Characteristics

The demographic breakdown of respondents is provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Male	160	72.72%
Female	60	27.28%
Age		
<35	120	54.5%
35-45	80	36.3%
>45	20	9.2%
Educational Level		
Senior high school or below	95	43.18%
Undergraduate	120	54.5%
Postgraduate or above	05	02.32%
Income		
2L-4.5L	115	52.02%
4.5L-6.5L	75	34.09%
6.5L-8.5L	30	13.89%

Key Factors Influencing Adoption

The key factors influencing E2W adoption, identified through inferential statistics, are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Key Factors Influencing Adoption of Electric Two-Wheelers

Factor	Mean Score
Price	4.5
Charging Infrastructure	4.2
Environmental Awareness	4.0
Social Reinforcement	3.8
Perceived Economic Benefits	4.1

Conclusion This study identifies critical factors influencing customer adoption of electric two-wheelers in India. Price, charging infrastructure, environmental awareness, social reinforcement, and perceived economic benefits significantly impact adoption rates. To enhance E2W adoption, manufacturers should focus on reducing costs, improving charging infrastructure, promoting environmental benefits, leveraging social influences, and highlighting economic advantages. Government policies should support these efforts through investments and incentives. Future research should explore additional factors and extend the analysis to other regions for comprehensive insights.

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